

FATIGUE CRACK RESISTANCE OF FRICTION STIR WELDED PMMC BUTT JOINTS

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SUMMARY: In this work the fatigue crack growth behaviour of an alumina particle-reinforced aluminum alloy friction stir welded (FSW) butt joint is characterized. Tests are conducted both in Stage I (near-threshold) and Stage II (Paris) regimes at two different R-ratios. Two crack position in the welded zone are considered, along the weld line and at the weld side, respectively. The increase of fatigue crack growth (FCG) rates with R-ratio has been evaluated in terms of crack closure, that in particulate metal matrix composites is generated mainly by crack surface roughness, crack deflection or trapping mechanisms, and in FSW joints is enhanced by residual stresses. Results are presented in a direct comparison with the parent material behavior. The specimen halves have been examined at the scanning electro microscope after fracture in order to highlight crack path features.

KEYWORDS: friction stir welding, metal matrix composite, fatigue crack propagation

1. INTRODUCTION

The Friction Stir Welding (FSW) technique is a welding process recently developed and patented by The Welding Institute (TWI) of Cambridge (UK). A general outline of the FSW process is depicted in Fig. 1. The process can be defined as a combination of hot extrusion and forging of the weld zone.

Fig. 1: (a) outline of the FSW process; (b) example of FSW application on a naval helideck.

So far, this technique has been employed especially in the naval and aerospace industries thanks to the capability of joining aluminum alloys with higher quality, strength and comparatively low cost with respect to more traditional welding techniques.

The extension of FSW to other materials has become a research topic in the last few years. As a solid-state joining process, FSW can be particularly effective in the case of materials sensitive to re-solidification after liquid-phase welding. This is indeed the case of Particulate Metal Matrix Composites (PMMC), which suffer from poor weldability with traditional processes due to the presence of ceramic particles. So far only few attempts have been made to produce and characterize PMMC, FSW joints [1], therefore leaving this field virtually unexplored. In this work, the fatigue crack resistance of an alumina particle-reinforced aluminum alloy FSW butt joint (figure 2) has been evaluated. Parameters of the experimental work are i) the position of the defect in the weld bead; ii) the $R = P_{\min}/P_{\max}$ load ratio. Differences in fatigue crack growth (FCG) rates at different R-ratio have been analysed considering crack closure development.

A crack path analysis has been eventually conducted at the SEM to assess: i) the presence of defects in the weld; ii) the crack-particles interaction during propagation in the weld; iii) the role of the load level on crack propagation mechanism through the measurement of the crack path roughness.

2. MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The composite under test is a 6061 aluminum alloy with 20% vol. of Al_2O_3 particles incorporated by compocasting. The mixture is then extruded and aged to obtain a bar of $100 \times 7 \text{ mm}^2$ cross-section in a T6 state. The tensile mechanical properties given by the manufacturer are reported in Tab. 1. The fracture toughness measured in a previous work [3] is reported instead in Tab. 2.

Fig. 2: (a) microstructure of PMMC base material and (b) microstructure across the weld.

Tab. 1: tensile mechanical properties of the parent plate.

Young's modulus E (GPa)	Yield strength R_s (MPa)	Tensile strength R_m (MPa)	Elongation $A\%$
97	360	375	4

Tab. 2: fracture toughness of the PMMC under investigation [1].

Direction	K_{IC} (MPa \sqrt{m})
LT	16.21
TL	15.38

The micrograph of Figs. 2a-b shows the high uniformity of particle distribution both in the base material and in the joint, where only a few isolated large particles and clusters are present. The particle size distribution has been analysed with the help of a commercial software. The results are summarized in the diagram of Fig. 3, from which it turns out that the majority has an area-equivalent diameter D_C of less than 3 microns.

Fig. 3: Particle size distribution a) in the base material and b) in the welded zone

Specimen and Crack Length Monitoring

A standard CT specimen geometry with a length $W = 24\text{mm}$ and thickness $B = 7\text{mm}$ was used in [1] to test the base material, while the joint was tested using an extended compact tension (ECT) geometry [3] (Fig. 4) with the same W and B but a height such to encompass the weld bead. The load P was controlled in both cases by means of a 3kN load cell in order to ensure adequate sensitivity and precision. The stress intensity factor calibration was taken from [3]. Since the small dimensions of the specimen did not allow to mount the standard clip-gage for COD measurement, the crack length was monitored during the test with the back-face strain gage (BFSG) technique. In this technique, a strain gage is attached to the back face of the specimen, as shown in Fig. 4, and a compliance-like value, C , can be determined from the back-face strain (ε) vs load (P) data:

$$C = \frac{-\varepsilon W}{P} \quad (1)$$

The crack length ratio a/W is then calculated by the test control software through the polynomial relationship:

$$\frac{a}{W} = a_0 + a_1 u + a_2 u^2 + a_3 u^3 + a_4 u^4 + a_5 u^5 \quad (2)$$

where

$$u = \frac{1}{1 + \sqrt{BEC}} \quad (3)$$

and the coefficients a_0, \dots, a_5 were determined by fitting the relationship given [3, 4] and validated by Finite Element Analysis (FEA).

Fig. 4: ECT specimen setup for the testing of the FSW joint.

Test method

The fatigue crack growth tests were conducted at a loading frequency of 10Hz in lab air. Constant load amplitude and continuous load-shedding procedures depending on the FCG rate range of interest were used. In constant load amplitude tests the applied cyclic load range (i.e. $\Delta P = P_{max} - P_{min}$) was kept constant throughout the test, while in the continuous load-shedding tests the load range was gradually decreased as the crack propagated according to [3]. As R-ratio dependence is expected to occur also in this class of materials, two load ratios $R = P_{min}/P_{max}$ (0.1 and 0.5, respectively) were investigated. In the case of the base material, both LT and TL crack orientations are considered. The FCG data are presented in log-log (da/dN vs. ΔK) plots. Crack propagation velocities were calculated by the secant method [3].

Crack roughness analysis

The roughness of the crack profile at the specimen side has been analysed at different values of the applied ΔK and compared with the values of the parent plate. The evaluation has been made by superimposing a grid on the image of the profile and counting the profile-grid intersections, $\sum n_i$, along a given length, L. The roughness R_v can be then expressed as:

$$R_v = \frac{y}{L} \sum n_i \quad (4)$$

This simple technique can obviously give only a monodimensional estimate of roughness.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

FCG rates

The diagram of Fig. 5 summarizes the tests made at the two different R-ratio and locations (WL=Weld Line; WS=Weld Side, see the scheme on the right). The influence of R-ratio is remarkable while the FCG data at the two different locations in the weld are practically superimposed.

Fig. 5: FCG rates.

The crack growth velocity in the interval 10^{-5} to 10^{-3} mm/cycle falls within the 95% prediction interval of the non-welded material for both R-ratios but in the near-threshold regime is considerably lower. This behaviour can be connected to at least two factors: i) reduction of the matrix grain size due to the heating and stirring and ii) residual stresses. The Stage I propagation mode [5] that generally develops at low stress intensities causes the crack path to be deflected at grain boundaries, therefore the lower the grain size the higher the number of deflection and, in turn, the shielding effect due to mixed-mode I/II loading conditions and roughness-induced crack closure (RICC). Concerning residual stresses, it has been demonstrated that their distribution in single-edge notched specimens (SEN) gives a higher closure level [6, 7]. The higher difference in FCG between base material and FSW joint found at $R=0.1$ with respect to $R=0.5$ can be justified also in these terms, since at the higher R-ratio only the residual stress contribution is active.

Fracture surface analysis

SEM micrographs of fracture surfaces are reported in Figs. 6-7. Crack propagation direction is from bottom to top. Two increasing magnifications of the same area are shown in each figure. The crack advances in a transcrystalline way in all of the cases analysed. At this level of stress intensity few instances of alumina particles are visible, as a result of the crack running mainly

inside the metal matrix. Some microvoids are however visible, that may be the result of particle decohesion and fracture. Elongated ridges are formed on the fracture surface in the WS crack since the matrix grains are generally distorted in that region due to stirring.

200x 1000x
 Fig. 6: fracture surface, WL crack, $\Delta K=9.8MPa\sqrt{m}$, $R=0.1$.

200x 1000x
 Fig. 7: fracture surface, WS, $\Delta K=9.9MPa\sqrt{m}$, $R=0.1$

The fracture surfaces of the FSW and of the PMMC parent plate are compared in Figs. 8a and 8b, respectively. The micrographs are taken at the same R-ratio and ΔK . The general aspect is very similar with some ridges and microvoids coming from particle decohesion and fracture, although they are smoother in FSW joints owing to the finer microstructure associated to the machining action.

(a) (a)
 Fig. 8: fracture surface of (a) FSW joint (WL) and (b) PMMC parent plate.

Results of roughness analysis are listed in Tab. 3, as a function of the propagation regime and for a R-ratio equal to 0.1.

Tab. 5: roughness of crack profile.

Material	R	R_v (μm) (near-threshold)	R_v (μm) (Paris regime)
Parent plate	0.1	0.22	0.51
FSW (WL)	0.1	0.41	0.48
FSW (WS)	0.1	0.50	0.64

It can be noticed that:

- a) *coeteris paribus* the roughness R_v is higher in the FSW joint;
- b) the increase in roughness of the FSW with respect to the parent plate is maximum in the near-threshold regime;
- c) WS crack shows a higher roughness of WL crack;

The higher roughness exhibited by the FSW joint especially at low ΔK s is in agreement with the interpretation of the difference in FCG rates with the parent plate in terms of RICC done previously. In addition, the difference in R_v between WL and WS helps to explain in terms of different levels of RICC the slightly lower FCG rates of cracks at WS in the near-threshold with respect to crack at WL under the same conditions.

The increase of roughness for increasing ΔK and load ratio is explained by the higher plastic deformation in the matrix. This is confirmed by the fact that in 7005/10p, where the matrix is more free to plastically deform due to the lower particle content, the roughness is generally higher.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Fatigue crack growth tests have been conducted on a FSW aluminum alloy reinforced with alumina particles. FCG rates at different R-ratios and crack locations have been compared with the results of tests on the parent plate done previously [1] and it turned out that the FSW joint is more resistant to crack propagation in the near-threshold regime. This difference has been explained qualitatively in terms of RICC and welding residual stresses. The analysis of fracture and crack roughness supported this explanation.

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